

Research article

Life cycle assessment and modeling approaches in silvopastoral systems: A case study of egg production integrated in an organic apple orchard

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ABSTRACT

This paper aimed to assess the environmental impacts of two organic silvopastoral farms in Austria, using a Life Cycle Assessment approach. The two farms (F1, F2), with egg production integrated into an apple orchard, were compared to standard practices for each product. The functional unit was '1 kg fresh Class I apples' and '1 kg fresh Class I eggs'. The assessment covered two scopes: cradle-to-farm gate and cradle-to-retail for each product. Effects on climate (including carbon sequestration in the soil and woody biomass), eutrophication potential (EP), acidification potential (AP), and land occupation (LO) were assessed. Feed, manure, and land were three resource loops included in the system boundary. Two modeling approaches were used from cradle-to-farm gate for distributing the impacts of the entire system between apples and eggs: model 1 (M1) used economic allocation, while model 2 (M2) divided the system into two subsystems. Results varied considerably by model. M1 consistently showed higher impacts for apples and considerably lower for eggs compared to M2. At farm gate, the carbon footprint (CF) ranged from 0.09 to 0.17 kg CO₂-eq/kg apple and 0.19–1.62 kg CO₂-eq/kg egg across all analyzed systems and models. Carbon sequestration reduced emissions by 22–42% for apples and by 0.4–39% for eggs. Sequestration was mainly associated with the carbon contributions from plant biomass from apple production (84–99%), with manure contributing 0.7–9%. EP ranged from 0.19 to 1.7 g PO₄-eq/kg apple and 0.7–35 g PO₄-eq/kg egg and AP ranged from 0.8 to 2.9 g SO₂-eq/kg apple and 2–36 g SO₂-eq/kg egg across all analyzed systems and models. LO ranged from 0.3 to 0.6 m²/kg apple and 0.8–9 m²/kg egg across all analyzed systems and models. Post-harvest activities accounted for up to 29% of the total impacts for EP and AP, and up to 57% for CF from cradle-to-retail. In general, the impacts per kg egg or kg apple in F1 and F2 were lower in most impact categories relative to their reference systems, driven mainly by management factors and the production phase of the value chain. Further development of modeling approaches is needed.

1. Introduction

Agriculture is a cornerstone of global livelihoods, playing a fundamental role in global food security (Ahmed et al., 2020). Perennial plantations, such as apple orchards, not only help sustain food production but also bring environmental benefits, including carbon (C) storage in the soil and plant biomass (Goossens et al., 2017). However, these systems can still place environmental pressure through the intensive use of fertilizers, herbicides, and pesticides (Bessou et al., 2013). Similarly, while well-managed animal production systems can enhance soil fertility by improving nutrient cycling through manure application

(Gliessman, 2014), they are also responsible for 14.5% of global anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Ahmed et al., 2020). Egg production, more specifically, while less land-intensive than ruminant systems, has its own environmental challenges, particularly through the demands of feed production and manure management (van Hal et al., 2019).

In Austria, agriculture is responsible for 9.5% of the total national emissions, primarily due to methane and nitrous oxides (Anderl et al., 2022). Among the key agricultural activities, apple and egg production are important components in the sector (Geßl, 2020). Apples are a major fruit crop, with Austria producing approximately 200,000 tons annually,

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much of it from organic orchards, with 76% of the total production concentrated in the Styria region (Muder et al., 2022). Similarly, organic egg production has expanded significantly, and Austria is now one of the leading countries in Europe in terms of free-range production (Augère-Granier, 2019). However, the environmental footprint within these systems needs to be addressed (Zaller et al., 2023).

Food from agroforestry systems (AFS) is a potential practice that can address the growing concerns over environmental degradation. Silvopastures are examples of AFS, where the integration of egg production in fruit orchards has the potential to close several resource loops beneficial for the environment. In Europe, the combination of fruit trees and animals is the most widely adopted form of agroforestry (accounting for 68% of the total AFS involving fruit production). However, this practice remains limited in scale compared to conventional orchards, representing only 0.24% of the total utilized agricultural area and 6% of the total area planted with fruit trees (Dodds et al., 2019). Despite its limited extent, these systems can potentially improve nutrient cycling and increase soil organic matter (Sollen-Norrlin et al., 2020). Additionally, hens can derive supplementary feed from foraging, potentially reducing the intake of concentrates (Paolotti et al., 2016; Bosshardt et al., 2022). Furthermore, multiple outputs can be delivered from the same unit of land, reducing land occupation (Escribano et al., 2022). However, integrating hens into perennial crop systems presents complex environmental interactions. For example, soils can be damaged due to pecking, scratching, overgrazing, and soiling (Sales-Baptista et al., 2016; Bosshardt et al., 2022). Additionally, nitrogen hotspots often accumulate in areas surrounding the hen houses, where manure deposition is concentrated (Bosshardt et al., 2022).

Modeling the above-mentioned environmental interactions can be a complex endeavor, and various scientific methods, levels of analysis, and indicators can be used to assess the environmental impacts of AFS. Among these methods, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a comprehensive tool that quantifies environmental impacts from a systems thinking perspective, encompassing the entire life cycle of a product or service (ISO, 2006a; Arvanitoyannis, 2008). Although LCA has been applied to AFS (Paolotti et al., 2016; Recanati et al., 2018; Lehmann et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2022), modeling silvopastoral systems remains a niche in the LCA literature and results vary greatly because of the different approaches used.

A recent review summarized some predominant methodological choices commonly used in LCAs of AFS (Quevedo-Cascante et al., 2023). For example, the C-seq potential is often omitted or included in very different ways, introducing difficulties in comparing results. In silvopastoral systems, C-seq is rarely accounted for in LCAs, and when included, the focus is often on soil, while C stored in woody biomass is often overlooked, highlighting a significant knowledge gap in LCAs of perennial systems (see e.g., Paolotti et al., 2016; Rosati et al., 2016; Tziolas et al., 2022). Only a handful of silvopastoral studies regarding dairy production (Brook et al., 2022) and beef and sheep meat (Mazzetto et al., 2023) address C-seq potential in the woody biomass, with reported offsets ranging from 26 to 28% (see e.g., Brook et al., 2022). In contrast, soil C-seq has been more frequently considered in silvopastoral studies involving cattle production (Reyes-Palomo et al., 2022), dairy goat production (Gutiérrez-Peña et al., 2019), and multiple livestock products (e.g., meat sheep, dairy goat, Iberian ham) (Horrillo et al., 2020), with reported emissions compensations between 35 and 100% (see e.g., Horrillo et al., 2020). Moreover, no LCAs involving egg or apple production have been found to account for C-seq, underscoring another important gap in the literature. Furthermore, existing LCA studies usually do not extend beyond farm gate assessment (see e.g., Escribano et al., 2018) and only a handful was found to conduct a comparative analysis of their standard system (Paolotti et al., 2016; Utomo et al., 2016). Thus, limiting the scope of the analysis of the differences between products from standard systems and AFS. Moreover, studies predominantly use a 'black box' approach to handle the multifunctionality of integrative systems (Mazzetto et al., 2023). Thus,

internal processes are not explicitly partitioned to specific farm outputs, suggesting a gap in knowledge for testing other approaches.

In response to such predominantly applied approaches in LCA studies, this paper has two objectives. First, to assess the environmental impacts and carbon footprint of two silvopastoral case studies in Austria, which involve egg production integrated into a perennial system (i.e., apple orchards), including a contribution analysis and considerations of C-seq and post-harvest activities. Second, to test two modeling approaches for handling multifunctionality at farm gate and compare the impact of the products from the assessed case studies to what is considered for each product, their standard and specialized practice.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. System description

The systems under analysis were based on two real-world silvopastoral farms located in Austria, in the Styria and Lower Austria provinces. This region is known for its significant apple production, featuring sandy and silty soils with an average pH of 6.5 and mean annual temperatures and precipitation levels of 10.6 °C and 800 mm, respectively. A map of the study area and the general silvopastoral configuration of the farms are shown in Fig. 1.

Two silvopastoral farms, Farm 1 (F1) and Farm 2 (F2), were purposively sampled (Phelan, 2011) because of their agroforestry activities, food-related products, farmers willingness to cooperate, and the availability and accessibility of empirical data. In addition, the two farms were sampled based on four key contrasting management practices, such as animal sourcing, animal density, replanting method, and between-row management (BRM). The selected farms were part of a larger network within the international European MIXED¹ project and relatively new in the agroforestry domain, having only recently incorporated animals (i.e., egg-laying hens and roosters) into their apple orchards. Farms had a well-established grass clover area and used drip tubing for irrigation. Compost was stored in windrows with infrequent turning and applied to both the agroforestry and non-agroforestry areas of the farmers' land. The duration and type of field operation were similar between the case studies and the reference system (per unit of area). All bird houses, built with similar materials, feature small wooden sheds with plastic grids, wooden perches, nests, windows, and round metal feeders and drinkers. Post-harvest activities were the same for all systems as they all followed organic farming principles. Thus, the systems were characterized by short value chains and distinguished between first-graded products (i.e., those that remained fresh for consumers, hereafter referred as to class I) and second-graded products (i.e., those that did not meet the market demands regarding size and esthetics and were transformed into processed products, hereafter referred as to class II). Technical characteristics are further summarized in Table 1.

- F1 had low stocking densities of hens in the orchard. F1 used spent hens (i.e., animals, bought from an organic farm after their first laying period) instead of pullets. After use, spent hens were either consumed at the farm or sent to a rendering plant at the end of their production cycle. Furthermore, trees were grafted with minimal soil disturbance, leaving fine and coarse roots in the soil. Biomass from pruning was partially used for mulching, and compost was mixed with manure and applied every five years. Animals were fed ad libitum with concentrates (i.e., mainly protein) and grains were supplemented from arable land (Table S2 in SD).

¹ MIXED is a project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 program and involves 14 networks of organic and conventional farmers across Europe (<https://projects.au.dk/mixed/about-mixed>).

a) Map of the study area

b) Silvopastoral systems description

Fig. 1. a) map of the study area. b) general farm structure and components (not at scale), including N flows across three environmental compartments (air, water, and soil).

Table 1

Technical characteristics of the systems under study were obtained from surveys for Farm 1 (F1), Farm (F2), reference system for apples (RS-A), and reference system for eggs (RS-E). Key management differences are indicated in bold.

Characteristics	Unit	F1	F2	RS-A	RS-E
General					
Land	ha	9	9.9	1	2.85
Average annual precipitation	mm/yr	800	880	840	840
Average annual temperature	°C	11	9	10	10
Production	system	Organic and biodynamic	Organic and biodynamic	Organic	Organic
Apple system					
Cultivars	Type	Topaz, Gala	Topaz, Gala	Topaz, Gala	–
Tree density	#/ha	2400	2400	2400	–
Apple yield	kg FM/ha/yr	30000	30000	30000	–
Irrigation system	Type	Drip irrigation	Drip irrigation	Drip irrigation	–
Fertilization ^a	kg N/yr	6	52	47	0
Between-row-management	type	Mulching	Mowing	Mowing	–
Replanting method	type	Grafting	Uprooting	Uprooting	–
Harvest method	type	Manual and mechanical	Manual and mechanical	Manual and mechanical	–
Egg system					
Total flocks	#	2	5	–	1
Breed	type	Traditional local	Lohman Brown	–	Lohman Brown
Egg yield	eggs/hen/yr	180	293	–	293
Egg laying performance	%	78–40	85–60	–	85–60
Annual bird population	#	116	877	–	2828
Hens (25–56 weeks)	#	0	699	–	2268
Pullets (18–24 weeks)	#	0	150	–	560
Spent hens (70 weeks)	#	112	0	–	0
Roosters (25–56 weeks)	#	4	28	–	0
Feed intake, total ^b	g DM/bird/day	90	96	–	121
Concentrates ^c	g DM/bird/day	84	90	–	115
Forage ^d	g DM/bird/day	6	6	–	6
Age entering the farm	weeks	70	18	–	18
Animal input	type	Spent hens	Pullets	–	Pullets
Average period in the farm	weeks	52	56	–	56
Mortality	%	40	20	–	20
Egg losses	%	1	5	–	5
Flock distribution	type	Mixed	Mixed	–	Mixed
Average egg weight	g/egg	60	62	–	62
Houses	#	2	5	–	1 ^e
Manure management	type	Pit storage	Pit storage	–	Pit storage
Artificial light	hrs/house/day	4	16	–	16

^a N related to the applied compost, excluding N inputs from manure deposition.

^b Detailed information regarding feed intake during the husbandry stage is in [Table S2 in SD](#), including ingredients produced at the non-agroforestry farm level.

^c All concentrates provided during the husbandry stage are imported to the agroforestry farm area.

^d All foraging activities happen within the agroforestry farm area.

^e Assuming one large building for all animals (equivalent to the materials and energy needed for 24 houses).

- F2 had a larger animal density in the orchard and almost double the egg yield per hen compared with F1. F2 used pullets for the replacement of hens at the end of their production cycle when the performance dropped to approximately 60%. Hens that reached the end of their production cycle were consumed or rendered. Animals received concentrates which was adjusted to cover the protein-rich feed requirements during winter and summer. Additionally, the feed was blended with grains harvested from the farmer's arable land ([Table S2 in SD](#)). Furthermore, after the end of the tree production cycle, deep plowing and coarse root excavation were undertaken for replanting new trees. All biomass from pruning was composted and mixed with sheep and bird manure. Compost was applied at least once a year.
- Reference systems: Two hypothetical farms associated with standard practices of non-integrated organic apples and egg production, respectively, were modeled using literature data and expert opinion. The reference system for apples (RS-A) was characterized by apple yields, tree densities, replanting methods, and BRM identical to those of F2. The specialized egg (RS-E) system was characterized by the same egg output as F2, and birds were fed complete concentrates ([Table S2 in SD](#)).

2.2. Goal and scope definition

This study followed the four methodological steps of LCA (ISO, 2006a, 2006b), namely, goal and scope definition, Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), and interpretation. The goal of this study was twofold. First, to assess the environmental impacts of two silvopastoral farms that exemplify an integrated apple and egg production system, along with respective value chains and their C-seq potential, using a comparative and attributional² LCA methodology. Second, to test two modeling approaches for handling multifunctionality at the farm gate and compare the case studies against their respective reference systems. The rationale for testing these models lies in their distinct approaches to addressing multifunctionality in integrated systems. Model 1 (M1), which employs a 'black box' approach, is the most commonly used approach in LCAs of AFS (Quevedo-Cascante et al., 2023). To provide a complementary perspective aligned with the higher ISO hierarchy for dealing with multifunctionality (ISO, 2006a), Model 2 (M2) was used, where the farm system is subdivided into two sub-systems. Both models are further detailed in [section 2.3.1.1](#). A product-based functional unit (FU) was used from cradle-to-farm gate

² A "process based modelling intended to provide a static representation of average conditions, excluding market-mediated effects" (FAO, 2020).

Table 2

Annual input and output data at the farm level related to the production of apples and eggs in Farm 1 (F1), Farm (F2), reference system for apples (RS-A), and reference system for eggs (RS-E). The table includes the applied allocation factors and carbon contributions for estimating sequestration in the soil and the woody biomass.

Input	Unit ^a	F1	F2	RS-A	RS-E
Animals	kg LW	209	1313	–	4188
Concentrates	kg	4051	32545	–	135282
Houses	p	0.1	0.3	–	1.6
Electricity	kWh/house	10	97	–	456
Straw (litter)	kg FM	365	456	–	2150
Water	m ³	7	56	–	233
Compost	kg N/ha	6	52	41	0
Phosphorous	kg P/ha	0.2	0.4	0.3	2.6
Irrigation	m ³ /ha	60	70	70	–
Plant protection	kg/ha	1.5	1.5	1.5	–
Planting and establishment	p	0.1	0.1	0.1	–
Field operations					
Harvest	hrs/ha	27	27	27	–
Pruning	hrs/ha	27	27	27	–
Between-row-management	hrs/ha	3	13	13	–
Plant protection	hrs/ha	23	23	23	–
Fertilization	hrs/ha	0.1	1	1	–
Maintenance	hrs/ha	5	5	5	–
Fertilization	hrs/ha	1	1	1	–
Uprooting	hrs/ha	0	1	1	–
Output					
Apple (total)	kg FM/yr	270000	297000	30000	–
Class I	kg FM/yr	237600	261360	26400	–
Class II	kg FM/yr	32400	35640	3600	–
Egg (total)	kg FM/yr	1200	14615	–	48718
Class I	kg FM/yr	1080	13154	–	43846
Class II	kg FM/yr	120	1462	–	4872
Animal Biomass ^b	kg LW	244	2192	–	7070
Manure	kg FM	30149	29092	0	–
	kg FM	0 ^c	0 ^c	–	52573
Sales price					
Apple Class I	euro/kg	2.9	2.9	2.9	–
Egg Class I	euro/kg	5.8	5.6	–	5.6
Apple Class II	euro/kg	0.6	0.6	0.6	–
Egg Class II	euro/kg	1.3	1.2	–	1.2
Spent hens	euro/kg	0	0.8	–	0.8
Share of Class I apples	%	88	88	88	–
Share of Class I eggs	%	90	90	–	90
Share of Class II apples	%	12	12	12	–
Share of Class II eggs	%	10	10	–	10
Allocation factor					
Apple Class I (M1)	%	96	88	97	–
Egg Class I (M1)	%	0.9	9	–	96
Spent hens (M1)	%	0	0.2	–	2
Apple Class I (M2)	%	97	97	97	–
Egg Class I (M2)	%	98	95	–	–
Spent hens (M2)	%	0	2	–	–
C-seq					
Compost mix	t C/ha	0.2	1.6	1.2	–
Manure (sheep) ^d	t C/ha	0	0.3	0	–
Manure (bird) ^e	t C/ha	0.01	0.3	0	–
Plant biomass ^f	t C/ha	0.2	0.9	1.2	–
Other biomass ^f	t C/ha	5.4	3.8	3.8	1.6
Pruning	t C/ha	0.8	0	0	–
Leaf litter	t C/ha	2.1	2.1	2.1	–
Roots (fine or coarse)	t C/ha	0.9	0.03	0.03	–
Crop residues	t C/ha	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6
Outdoor manure deposition	t C/ha	0.03	0.2	0	2.6

Table 2 (continued)

Input	Unit ^a	F1	F2	RS-A	RS-E
Total input to the soil	t C/ha	5.6	5.6	4.3	5.0
C that remains in soil (100-year)	t C/ha	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.03
C-seq (100-year) (soil)	t CO ₂ -eq/ha	0.6	0.6	0.4	0.1
C that remains in the woody AGB (100-year)	t C/ha	0.10	0.14	0.14	–
C accumulation rate ^g	t C/ha	2.9	3.8	3.8	–
C-seq (100-year) (woody biomass)	t CO ₂ -eq/ha	0.38	0.52	0.52	0

^a FM = fresh matter; LW = live weight; p = pieces; kWh = kilowatt-hour; C=Carbon; hrs = hours; ha = hectare.

^b Refers to the biomass from pruning residues in kg DM exported to the farmers' non-agroforestry farm.

^c Given the lower stocking densities and larger land area in F1 and F2, it was assumed that all manure excreted by hens inside the bird houses was applied to the agroforestry fields, with no manure exported.

^d Quantities in kg DM were reported by farmers and then converted into t C/ha as explained in section 2.3.1.4.

^e Quantities in kg DM were estimated as explained in section 2.3.1.2 and then converted into t C/ha as explained in section 2.3.1.4.

^f Quantities estimated as explained in section 2.3.1.4.

^g Over one rotation cycle (15-years).

and cradle-to-retail for the reference year of 2021 and defined as: (i) “1 kg of fresh Class I apples” and “1 kg of fresh Class I eggs”. This FU was used because it distinguished the impacts per unit of each product, which enabled direct comparison with other LCAs focused on similar products.

Since the focus of this paper was on the supply side of the value chain (a critical stage for assessing the silvopastoral integration), the system boundary (Fig. 2) was from cradle-to-retail and was divided into two main assessments: food production (cradle-to-farm gate) and post-harvest (cradle-to-retail) both for each product. The post-harvest assessment focused solely on the value chain associated with Class I products. The system boundary considered three resource loops related to the silvopastoral interaction (i.e., manure, land, and feed) and one resource loop mainly related to apple production (i.e., biomass). The inventory data was a combination of farm data reported by farmers and average data from previous years to ensure that the assessment reflected the impacts of standard conditions. Furthermore, activity data for the apple management subphase were solely considered for the high production years (assuming the orchard is 8 years old).

2.3. Life cycle inventory

Activity data (i.e., input quantities) linked to the foreground and background processes for each subphase depicted in Fig. 2 were compiled using a three-step procedure. First, a comprehensive survey protocol was developed and empirical data were systematically collected by the local experts at the two farms. Second, after synthesizing data obtained from the survey protocol, online interviews and questionnaires were conducted with the local experts for further clarification. Third, in-situ farm observations were conducted and complemented by informal interviews with farmers. The interviews were recorded and transcribed for further data extraction and validation. Ongoing dialogue was maintained throughout the assessment with local experts.

2.3.1. Cradle-to-farm gate

2.3.1.1. Modeling approaches for the silvopastoral systems. This paper followed a gross nitrogen (N) mass balance approach (OECD, 2007; Sainju, 2017) and used country-specific methodologies (i.e., Austrian

Fig. 2. System boundary. Phases and sub-phases for the apple and egg value chain.

national inventory) and farm-specific data, when available, to calculate N and Phosphorus (P) turnover, emissions, soil C and N changes, and leaching (hereafter referred as flows). Four phases were included (i.e., housing, storage, application, and deposition) to estimate the flows occurring in the production system (at the flock, field, and farm level) and were calculated based on dry matter (DM) content. Input and output data related to the production of apples and eggs at farm level is shown in Table 2.

Two modeling approaches (Fig. 3) were applied at the farm level to distribute the flows associated with apple and egg production across the four phases. In M1, emissions were modeled using the most common modeling approach in the LCA literature. This method used a ‘black-box’ approach, where the flows were allocated according to the economic

value of the products and co-products at the farm gate. In M2, the farm system was partitioned into two subsystems. The emissions associated with the manure excreted during the housing and deposition phase were assigned to the egg subsystem because these emissions were directly associated with the animal production system and were part of the free-range system’s normal operations. Whereas emissions associated with the storage and application phase of manure were credited to the system applying/using it (i.e., the apple subsystem). Thus, only emissions from the manure that was stored and transformed were credited to apples, while emissions from manure deposited during grazing were assigned to eggs in M2. This follows the same logic applied to manure excreted during the housing phase, where non-transformed manure was entirely credited to the egg subsystem. Consequently, C-seq and soil N changes

Fig. 3. Farm level models where a) model 1 and b) model 2, including N flows (black arrows) and other N inputs (white arrows). The emissions and losses assigned to the apple- and egg-subsystem throughout the four phases (housing, storage, application, and deposition) are in red and yellow, respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

associated with outdoor manure deposition (and crop residues) were also credited entirely to the egg subsystem in M2.

2.3.1.2. N balance at farm level. Table 3 shows the N balances and the corresponding losses of N flows at the farm level. These N flows are then allocated to eggs and apples based on M1 and M2 approaches. The N balance considered the flows of the resource loops specified in Fig. 2. Atmospheric deposition was assumed to be 16 kg N/ha, based on the average values for Eastern Austria (Brentrup et al., 2000), which was aligned with other literature values (Halberg et al., 2010; Knudsen et al., 2010). Moreover, the crude protein (CP) content in apples was assumed to be 2 g per fresh apple, which is consistent with the figures reported in OECD (2019). Additionally, it was assumed that the understory vegetation was a mix of red clover, ryegrass, and herb ley with a biological fixation of 26 kg N/ha (Goh and Ridgen, 1997). This value was corroborated by local experts and other studies (Gentile, 2022). The same N-fixation rate was used across all systems, as the total N input per ha was relatively low in all cases, assuming no negative impact in N-fixation. Data on farm gate prices were used to estimate the allocation factors (AF) for apples (classes I and II) and eggs (classes I and II). Since F1 reported buying spent hens for 2 euros/bird from RS-E, it was assumed that the animals had economic value in both RS-E and F2 for a fair comparison. In F1, the spent hens bought from RS-E were sent to a rendering plant or consumed at the farm at the end of their production cycle. Thus, animals in F1 were considered as residuals (i.e., no emission burden). Economic AFs were used with the farm co-products/residuals (i.e., spent hens) to align with the allocation approach used for class I and II products in all systems and models. In M2, economic allocation

followed the same method as in M1, but only included products within each subsystem. In the apple subsystem (F1, F2, RS-A), allocation was between Class I and II apples. In the egg subsystem (F2, RS-E), it was between Class I and II eggs and spent hens (due to their economic value). For the egg subsystem in F1, allocation was only between Class I and II eggs, as spent hens were considered residuals. Equations used for determining the N flows are further described in supplementary data (SD) in Table S1.

Inventory data for the apple and egg production subsystems were compiled for each subphase, as illustrated in Fig. 2. For areas lacking specific information, background data representing upstream generic production values were compiled using the Agribalyse 3 database (Agribalyse, 2020). The annual average animal population was calculated for populations with and without roosters and was determined based on the initial reported batch, the annual replacement of animals at the end of their production cycle, and the annual replacement of animals with pullets or spent hens, following mortality. The calculation of the total N excretion was determined from feed N-intake and N retained by the animals and eggs (excluding roosters), taking into consideration lost eggs. The total annual N excretion during the housing and deposition phase was determined based on the proportion of the year that animals spent indoor and outdoor, as reported by farmers.

The average content of N in live weight (LW) and eggs was assumed to be 28.8 g N/kg LW gain and 18.1 g N/kg egg, respectively (Poulsen et al., 2001). N content in organic feed and forage intake was determined through the CP percentage of DM (since N comprises on average 16% of the total weight of protein) reported in the Danish national feed intake tables for each ingredient. The average DM removal of herbage by laying

Table 3

Estimations of N balances at farm level (within the system boundaries, excluding non-agroforestry land) for Farm 1 (F1), Farm (F2), reference system for apples (RS-A), and reference system for eggs (RS-E), including leaching in kg N/ha/year and other N losses.

Input	F1	F2	RS-A	RS-E
	kg N/ha/ yr	kg N/ha/ yr	kg N/ha/ yr	kg N/ha/ yr
Concentrates feed	8	77	0	1208
Animal population ^a	1	4	0	42
Atmospheric deposition	16	16	16	16
Compost (other manure)	0	19	0	0
Biological fixation	26	26	26	26
Spelt (litter)	0	0	0	4
Total input	51	143	42	1297
Outputs				
Apples	10	10	10	0
Eggs	2	27	0	309
Animal population	1 ^b	6 ^c	0	71 ^c
Manure (exported) ^d	0	0	0	250
Biomass (exported) ^d	23	20	0	0
Total output	35	63	10	631
Balance/Surplus	15	80	32	666
Soil N changes^e	-16	-15	-10	-3
Tree growth	14	14	14	0
Losses				
N ₂ O-N (direct)	0.2	1	1	6
NH ₃ -N	3.8	21	7	214
NO-N	0.9	5	3	29
Total - direct	5.0	27	10	248
N ₂ O-N (indirect)	-0.2	0	0.05	7
Total - indirect	-0.2	0.5	0.05	7
Potential leaching NO₃-N	-20	23	-2	408^f

^a Animal population represents the average N from the annual live weight of animals entering or exiting the farm.

^b Residual. 50% for human consumption and 50% sent to rendering plant (i.e., economic AF = 0).

^c Assuming spent hens have an economic value.

^d Residual. Pruning residues exported to arable land (i.e., economic AF = 0).

^e Negative values refer to C-seq.

^f The high leaching is due to RS-E reflecting only the outdoor run area, while F1 and F2 include the total orchard area.

hens during foraging was assumed to be 18 g DM/bird/day based on measurement by Horsted et al. (2006), assuming an average DM content of 12% and a CP of 21%. The total intake was estimated based on the number of days and hours that the animals spent outdoors during the year. It was assumed the same feed and forage intake for roosters, mature hens, and pullets older than 18 weeks of age. Table S2 in SD provides details on feed intake, encompassing the ingredients and their CP. It was assumed that additional calcium was consumed from the soil to fulfill the recommended 7.5 g of calcium intake per bird. This was based on observational field data indicating no signs of calcium deficiency in the eggs. Foraging was assumed to have no impact burdens for the egg subsystem in all models and analyzed systems.

2.3.1.3. Estimating emissions. Emissions during the housing and storage phases were calculated based on the reported N for organic fresh chicken manure (6.1%), green compost (1.2%), and sheep manure (2.7%) (Landwirtschaftskammer, 2010). Depending on the farm, the amount of N in compost – in addition to the N in the collected bird manure excreted indoors – includes N inputs from organic biomass (i.e., pruning biomass) and other manure (i.e., sheep manure). Emission factors (EFs) representing losses associated with N substances are indicated in Table S3 in SD.

NH₃ emissions were calculated using the EMEP/EEA Tier 2

approach, which uses EFs expressed per unit of total ammoniacal nitrogen (TAN) excreted for each of the examined phases (Anderl et al., 2022, Table 219). Direct N₂O emissions from managed soils were calculated using the Tier 2 approach (IPCC, 2019b) and country-specific N excretion rates by considering N in organic fertilizer (i.e., compost) and N in urine and dung deposited during foraging. In addition to direct N₂O emissions from managed soils originating from direct applications, N₂O is also released through two indirect pathways, N volatilization and deposition and N leaching and runoff (IPCC, 2019b). Indirect N losses due to volatilization and leaching from manure management were calculated according to Tier 2 methodology. Tier 1 default EFs for solid manure storage and compost application were used to estimate NO and NO₃ emissions (Anderl et al., 2022). Activity data were then multiplied by a representative EF according to its disaggregated climatic zone (i.e., cool temperate moist climate) and fertilizer type when applicable, as specified in IPCC (2019b). The values were then converted to NH₃, N₂O, NO, and NO₃ emissions (IPCC, 2019a, 2019b). The potential N left for leaching and runoff (NO₃-N) was calculated by subtracting the N outputs, N losses, and N uptake (trees and soil N changes). The soil N changes were assumed to be linked with the below-ground biomass soil C pool (described in section 2.3.1.4), assuming a carbon-to-nitrogen (C: N) ratio of 10. The yearly N uptake in trees (roots, branches, and trunks) was assumed to be 6 g/tree based on Neilsen et al. (2001). These estimates align with figures from Lepp et al. (2024) and Geßl (2020) (i.e., 7.5 g/stone and pome fruit trees).

Total P losses during the application phase at the orchard level were modeled using a P₂O₅ content of 0.3% in the compost (Landwirtschaftskammer, 2010). The EF was estimated using the Tier 1 approach and was defined as the amount of P applied to agricultural fields by foraging and compost and the runoff from soil to water, as explained in PEFCE (2018). For enteric fermentation CH₄, the IPCC Tier 2 approach was used, in which EFs were developed based on Swiss data, as proposed by the Austrian National Inventory (Anderl et al., 2022). This is because Swiss farming practices and conditions were similar to those of Austria. Country-specific EFs were developed for manure management, and the Tier 2 method was used (IPCC, 2019a). Although the excreted manure during housing is managed in multiple systems across the storage and application phases (i.e., pit storage below animal confinement and composting), EFs were calculated according to the fraction of the dominant indoor and outdoor manure management system (i.e., composting with passive windrows and pasture/range/paddock, respectively) and selected according to the dominant climate zone (i.e., temperate moist), as suggested by IPCC (2019a). Default values for CH₄, conversion of N and P emissions, and environmental indicators and characterization factors are in Table S4 in SD.

2.3.1.4. Soil carbon changes and carbon sequestration. A combination of models and methods was used to estimate the potential C-seq and soil C changes. First, the C inputs associated with the belowground biomass (BGB) and woody aboveground biomass (AGB) were quantified. Regarding BGB, the soil C inputs associated with the woody biomass (i.e., leaf litter, pruning residues, and roots) were estimated using allometric functions for apple trees (Ledo et al., 2018). The soil C inputs of the crop residues were estimated according to Mogensen et al. (2018) using coefficients for dry matter allocation of aboveground residues (0.7) and belowground residues (0.4) for perennial grass. The soil C inputs of the compost mix and bird manure were determined based on the N balance and assuming a C:N ratio of 30 and 9, respectively (Brust, 2019; Rynk et al., 2021). Carbon sequestered in AGB, including the trunk, branches, and stem, as well as in BGB (fine and coarse roots) and leaves, was estimated using the Perennial GHG model as described by Ledo et al. (2018) for a complete rotation cycle of 15 years. This model was specifically parameterized for apple trees (Ledo et al., 2018). A key distinction between farms F1 and F2 was the method of harvesting after the rotation cycle. In F1, farmers only removed the woody AGB, and

Table 4

Summary of results for the apple and egg subsystem in each impact category in this paper from cradle-to-farm gate for Farm 1 (F1), Farm (F2), reference system for apples (RS-A), and reference system for eggs (RS-E) using Model 1 (M1) and Model 2 (M2).

	CF (kg CO ₂ -eq) ^a		EP (g PO ₄ -eq)		AP (g SO ₂ -eq)		LO	
	per kg apple	per kg egg	per kg apple	per kg egg	per kg apple	per kg egg	per kg apple	per kg egg
This paper:								
Reference	0.104 (0.071)	1.620 (1.613)	0.28	35	1.3	44	0.37	6.8
F1								
M1	0.094 (0.058)	0.192 (0.118)	<i>0.35</i>	0.7	1.0	2	<i>0.41</i>	0.8
M2	0.089 (0.051)	1.349 (1.324)	0.19	35	0.8	36	0.37	9.3
F2								
M1	<i>0.171 (0.134)</i>	0.338 (0.271)	<i>1.75</i>	3.5	<i>2.9</i>	6	<i>0.62</i>	1.2
M2	<i>0.109 (0.068)</i>	1.537 (1.520)	<i>0.51</i>	28	<i>1.6</i>	33	0.37	6.1

^a In brackets, net emissions with C inputs contributing to sequestration. Values in cursive or bold are higher or lower relative to the reference system (in regular font), respectively.

after cutting the stem, coarse and fine roots were left in the soil, contributing gradually to C input through decomposition over 100 years. In contrast, in F2, farmers removed both the stem and roots, leaving only fine roots to contribute to soil C. Fine roots have a short lifespan and detach from the main roots annually. It was assumed that fine roots die each year and were replaced by new ones, with dead roots contributing to the soil C pool. Thus, in F2, only fine roots were considered as C input to the soil. The model by Kurz et al. (1996) was used to estimate the proportion of fine roots remaining as the tree aged. Pruning began in year five, with the proportion of biomass pruned from years five to fifteen following the pattern: 5%, 10%, 10%, 10%, 10%, 12%, 12%, 12%, 12%, and 12%. For F2, the pruned biomass was composted, while leaves decomposed directly into the soil, contributing to soil organic C. In F1, the pruned biomass was left on the soil as mulch. C content of dry woody AGB, leaves biomass, and BGB was 0.47%, 0.47%, and 0.44%, respectively (Ledo et al., 2018; Li et al., 2019). C stored in fruits was not included in the analysis, as the fruits were harvested and removed from the field. The C-seq associated with the AGB was estimated using the methodology by Clift and Brandao (2008). Allometric functions used in the study are provided in SD below Table S5.

Second, soil C-seq associated with the C inputs from the BGB was estimated following the methodology proposed by Petersen et al. (2013), where it was assumed that approximately 10% of the C added to soils, under an average air temperature of 8 °C, would be sequestered over 100 years. Given that the mean average air temperature was 10 °C, it was assumed that a 10% estimate was applicable for this paper. To

estimate potential C release or sequestration, Danish wheat was chosen as a reference crop like in Mogensen et al. (2014). The difference in total C input from the wheat crop (i.e., 397 kg C/ha/yr) (Mogensen et al., 2018) was calculated for each orchard and reference system and multiplied by 10% to obtain the effect of soil C changes on atmospheric CO₂ over a 100-year perspective. This timeframe was chosen in this paper because it aligns with the 100-year time horizon used for the CF. Data important for the C-seq estimations are specified in Table S5 in SD. A graphical description can be found in Fig. S1 in SD.

2.3.1.5. Land occupation. Land occupation (LO) in m²a/kg class I product (apple or egg) was estimated for three stages at farm gate: (i) the rearing stage included the LO linked to the background data associated with the concentrates for raising pullets or spent hens, (ii) the husbandry stage included the foreground data associated with the reported concentrates for raising animals during the laying period, and (iii) the farm area included the foreground data associated with the orchard production. Average inventory data from Agribalyse 3 (Agribalyse, 2020) were used for feed production and primary data for the farm area. The total LO was estimated by adding the physical land area used in the three stages. Subsequently, the total LO was allocated to apples and eggs according to their economic value for class I products and then divided by the Class I yield. The AFs were based on those estimated for M1 and M2 (Table 3). For apples and eggs, M1 accounted for the LO in the three stages. For eggs, M2 included the LO from feed production, excluding the farm area. For apples, M2 included the LO from the farm area only,

Table 5

Sensitivity analysis (SA) at farm gate for apples and eggs and percentage differences of methodological choices and assumptions for Farm 1 (F1), Farm (F2), reference system for apples (RS-A), and reference system for eggs (RS-E).

	Apples					Eggs				
	RS-A	F1		F2		RS-E	F1		F2	
		M1	M2	M1	M2		M1	M2	M1	M2
Baseline (kg CO₂-eq/kg)^a	0.104	0.094	0.089	0.171	0.109	1.62	0.192	1.35	0.34	1.54
a) Manure as waste (M3)	-	-	-1%	-	-4%	-	-	9%	-	6%
Baseline (g PO₄-eq/kg)	0.29	0.35	0.19	1.8	0.5	35	0.7	35	3.5	28
a) Manure as waste (M3)	-	-	-14%	-	-52%	-	-	14%	-	14%
Baseline (g SO₂-eq/kg)	1.33	1.0	0.83	2.9	1.6	44	2.0	36	5.8	33
a) Manure as waste (M3)	-	-	-3%	-	-13%	-	-	13%	-	11%
Baseline (m²a/kg)	0.37	0.41	0.37	0.62	0.37	6.8	0.83	9.3	1.2	6.1
b) LO AF to eggs	-	-	-1.3%	-	-9%	-	-	10%	-	10%
Baseline (kg CO₂-eq/kg)^b	0,07	0,058	0,051	0,13	0,07	1,61	0,12	1,32	0,27	1,52
c) Lower AGB C-seq	16%	14%	16%	8%	17%	-	14%	-	7%	-

Red color: SA is higher than the baseline.

Green color: SA is lower than the baseline.

^aWithout C-seq

^bWith C-seq

excluding feed production. A graphical description can be found in Fig. S2 in SD. Furthermore, since a large share of feedstuffs (i.e., maize and wheat) were reported to be produced locally in this paper, it was assumed that there was no direct land use change (dLUC). Similar to Knudsen et al. (2019), the rest of the feed compounds were assumed to be produced at the national level, and soybean compounds were assumed to be imported from China, and thus, dLUC was assumed to be zero.

2.3.2. Cradle-to-retail

Data on post-harvest activities for apples and eggs were only collected for those categorized into class I across two phases: (i) sorting, storage, and packaging and (ii) retail. Distribution-related activities were excluded because a local cooperative was responsible for managing the distribution to retail outlets (as opposed to wholesalers), along with overseeing bulk storage, processing, and packaging operations. Transportation mode, vehicle type, and distance only accounted for off-site activities (i.e., transportation to warehouses in cooperatives and retailers outside farm boundaries). This was because the distances on-site (i.e., at the farm level) were small and considered negligible and accounted for during harvest. A summary of the data used for the two phases is in Table S6 in SD.

During the sorting, storage, and packaging phase, 88% of harvested apples were sorted on-site as class I. All storage occurred off-site at local cooperative facilities. Apples were transported in 300 kg high-density polyethylene pallet bins in refrigerated trucks and stored at 4 °C using controlled atmosphere technology. Data for energy use during storage were based on literature (Boschiero et al., 2019). No packaging materials were used (except for the pallet bins) as class I apples were sold unpacked in bulk. Storage losses were 1%. For eggs, 90% of fresh eggs were sorted on-site as class I. Initial sorting and minimal packaging occurred on-site, with further packaging off-site at cooperative facilities. Packaging materials included corrugated boards, cartons, and labels, transported by various means to the national market. Estimated weights were 390 g for external boxes, 80 g for corrugated boxes, and 15 g for labels (Abbate et al., 2023). Packaging losses were 1%. During the retail phase, class I apples were sold off-site with an assumed 5% loss at retail (Le Féon et al., 2023). Retail considerations included water, energy use, and refrigerated transport. For eggs, 90% of class A eggs were sold off-site, with the remainder sold on-site. Retail considerations included transport to regional and international retailers and water and energy consumption for cooling and cleaning. Retail losses were assumed to be 2% (Kanyama, 2016).

2.4. Life cycle impact assessment

The LCIA was conducted using SimaPro 9.3.0.3 (PRé Sustainability, Amersfoort, Netherlands) and the CML-baseline, which was adapted to the latest IPCC AR6 and Climate Carbon Feedback (CCF) characterization factors. Incorporating CCF entails the consideration of potential additional warming or cooling effects arising from feedback mechanisms. This approach aligns with the overarching objective of capturing long-term climate impacts (e.g., in a 100-year perspective). The CML-baseline LCIA method was chosen because (i) it contains the most common impact categories used in LCA (Merchan and Combelles, 2012), (ii) it has shown strong correlations with other LCIA methods (Pak et al., 2023), and (iii) the combination of its indicators exhibited minimal dependencies (i.e., changes in one indicator did not significantly affect others, making it easier to discern the unique contributions of the selected impact categories) (Pak et al., 2023). Four impact categories were considered: (i) Carbon Footprint (CF) in kg CO₂-eq, (ii) Eutrophication Potential (EP) in g PO₄-eq, (iii) Acidification Potential (AP) in g SO₂-eq, and (iv) Land Occupation (LO) in m²a. The selection of these impact categories was based on their alignment with the N balance methodology, which enabled a robust assessment of N and P flows and turnover, shedding light on their impacts on the air, soil, and water

compartments, as shown in Fig. 1.

The contribution analysis for CF, EP, and AP included nine activities linked to off-farm (OFF) and on-farm (ONF) emissions: (i) feed production (OFF emissions related to the production of feed provided during the husbandry stage, i.e., imported feed), (ii) field operations (ONF emissions related to the operation, production, and maintenance of machineries, including copper sulfate production), (iii) bird rearing (OFF emissions related to the production of pullets or spent hens), (iv) compost mix (ONF emissions related to the storage and application phase according to Fig. 3), (v) bird manure (ONF emissions related to the housing and deposition phase according to Fig. 3, including storage only for RS-E), (vi) buildings (OFF emissions related to the materials used for the hen houses, including litter, and water and electricity consumption), (vii) orchard establishment (ONF emissions related to tree nursery, planting, and orchard establishment), (viii) C-seq in the soil (ONF emissions related to C-seq in the soil), and (ix) C-seq in the woody biomass (ONF emissions related to C-seq in the woody biomass). The contribution analysis for LO included the three stages explained in section 2.3.1.5.

2.5. Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis (SA) was performed to address uncertainties stemming from key methodological assumptions and data choices. Two variables representing the resource loop were modified individually to analyze their effects on the LCIA: (a) manure classification by modeling it as a waste, hereafter called Model 3 (M3) (Fig. S3 in SD), where all manure-related emissions were assigned 100% to the egg subsystem (assuming no interactions) and (b) LO, where the minimum farm area required for birds were allocated to the egg subsystem in M2 for F1 and F2, in order to determine the land savings from the integration. In addition, (c) only the values for C accumulation rates in the woody AGB were reduced by 64%, from 2.98 to 1.1 t C/ha/yr in F1 and 3.8 to 1.4 t C/ha/yr in F2, aligning more closely with average values reported in some literature (Zanotelli et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2020; McNally and Gentile, 2021). Other parameters (e.g., pruning residues and leaf litter) were the same.

3. Results

3.1. Cradle-to-farm gate

In general, the environmental impacts per kg egg or kg apple in F1 and F2 are lower in most impact categories relative to their reference systems (RS-E and RS-A). The total impact per farm (which is the same across models) is shown in Fig. 4. Results are discussed in more detail under each subsection. A summary of the results from cradle-to-farm gate is shown in Table 4.

The total farm emissions are the same in both models (M1 and M2). However, the way these emissions are distributed to different products (apples, eggs, spent hens) varies significantly, leading to distinct results for each model. In M1, economic allocation distributes the emissions based on the relative market value of the different products, resulting in lower emissions attributed to eggs. In contrast, M2 partitions the farm into two subsystems, where emissions are more directly linked to the processes associated with each product. As a result, emissions per kg egg in M2 are higher compared to per kg egg in M1. The increase in egg-related emissions in F2 compared to F1 was driven by the greater number of hens, feed consumption (0.9 kg N/bird in F2 compared to 0.6 kg N/bird in F1), manure deposition, and pullet rearing.

3.1.1. Climate change

The CF for apples without contributions of C in the soil and the woody biomass is between 0.09 and 0.17 kg CO₂-eq/kg apple (Fig. 5). The contribution analysis showed that field operations contribute between 50 and 91% of the total emissions. The second major contributor

Fig. 4. Total farm emission distribution across class I (I - Apples; I - Eggs), class II (II - Apples; II - Eggs), and other co-products (Spent hens, after the end of production cycle) for Farm 1 (F1) and Farm (F2), including carbon footprint in t CO₂-eq, eutrophication potential in kg PO₄-eq, and acidification potential in kg SO₂-eq. Minor differences between models are attributed to rounding effects during data processing.

Fig. 5. Carbon footprint (CF) per kg apple (left) and per kg egg (right) in kg CO₂-eq using two modeling approaches (M1, M2) for Farm 1 (F1), Farm (F2), reference system for apples (RS-A), and reference system for eggs (RS-E). CF without contribution from C-seq (top) and net CF taking into account contribution from soil C changes and C-seq in the woody biomass (below).

is emissions from the compost mix (4–14%). Due to the economic allocation used in M1, feed production also contributes to the CF of apples (5% for F1 and 23% for F2). Emissions linked to the establishment of apple trees contribute less than 1% of the total emissions in all systems and models. The CF of F1 is lower than RS-A, while F2 is higher than RS-A. Regarding eggs, the CF is between 0.19 and 1.62 kg CO₂-eq/kg egg. Feed production (5–75%), bird manure (1–20%), and bird rearing (0.2–32%) are important contributors across all systems and models. The emissions from field operations are only notable in M1 and minor contributions (less than 4%) are from buildings. Overall, RS-E has a higher CF than F1 and F2. In M1, apples receive a greater share of emissions due to their higher economic value, resulting in lower CF per kg of eggs. F2's higher egg yields further increase the allocation factor, leading to higher emissions per kg apple compared to F1. In M2, differences between F1 and F2 for both apples and eggs are mainly due to management practices, such as compost application and feed production, with F1 benefiting from the use of spent hens and F2 showing higher emissions due to pullets.

Fig. 5 c) and d) show the net CF per kg apple and eggs. C-seq reduces the CF in F1 and F2 by 22–42% for apples and 1–39% for eggs. In the reference systems, C-seq contributes to reductions of 32% and 0.4% for RS-A and RS-E, respectively. Thus, considering all systems and models, emissions were reduced by 22–42% for apples and by 0.4–39% for eggs. C inputs contributing to soil C-seq differ across farms and are shown in Fig. S4 in SD. In F1, most C inputs are from pruning (14%), leaf litter (38%), roots (15%), crop residues (29%), and bird manure (0.7%). In F2, C contributions are from leaf litter (38%), crop residues (29%), and bird manure (9%). In RS-E, 62% of C inputs are from manure and 38% from crop residues. In RS-A, the C contributions are from compost (25%), leaf litter (42%), and crop residues (32%).

3.1.2. Eutrophication potential

EP for apples is between 0.19 and 1.7 g PO₄-eq/kg apple (Fig. 6). Main contributors to EP across all systems and models are compost mix (19–73%), field operations (7–64%), and feed production (25–39%). RS-A has a lower EP, except for F1M2. EP for eggs is between 0.7 and 35 g PO₄-eq/kg egg. Bird manure and feed production represent a considerable share of EP with values between 18–53% and 25–56%, respectively. Bird rearing represents up to 9% of the total impact. Overall, RS-E has a higher EP, with M1 having a lower EP relative to all systems and models. In M1, emissions from egg production are economically allocated to apples where higher egg yields result in a larger allocation factor and share of emissions (0.9%–9% for eggs in F1 and F2, respectively), which also explains the lower impacts per kg egg in F1 and F2. In M2, the differences between F1 and F2 are driven by management choices, such as the fertilization rates for apples and feed production and outdoor manure excretion for eggs.

Fig. 6. EP per kg apple (left) and per kg egg (right) in kg PO₄-eq using two modeling approaches (M1, M2) for Farm 1 (F1), Farm (F2), reference system for apples (RS-A), and reference system for eggs (RS-E).

3.1.3. Acidification potential

AP for apples is between 0.8 and 2.9 g SO₂-eq/kg apple (Fig. 7). Contributions are primarily due to compost mix (22–57%) and field operations (21–74%). Except for F2, RS-A has a higher AP. For eggs, values are between 2 and 36 g SO₂-eq/kg egg, with main contributions from bird manure (11–68%), feed production (5–30%), and bird rearing (1–22%). Like EP, M1 has a lower AP across all systems and models, with RS-E having a higher AP. Similar to EP and CF, in M1, the economic allocation factor places more environmental burden on apples, reducing the AP per kg egg. In F2, the higher egg yields further increase the allocation factor to apples, resulting in higher AP per kg apple compared to F1. Under M2, the direct allocation of impacts to subsystems means that management practices, such as fertilization rates and manure management, drive the differences in AP between F1 and F2 for apples. For eggs, the higher AP in F2 is attributed to the greater amount of manure excreted outdoors and feed production, compared to F1.

3.1.4. Land occupation

Total LO is shown in Fig. 8, with values ranging between 0.3 and 0.6 m²/kg apple and 0.8–9 m²/kg egg, respectively. Except for M1, RS-A has the same LO compared to F1 and F2. For eggs, M1 has a lower LO by approximately an order of magnitude than M2 across all systems. The LO for egg production is up to 25-fold greater than that for apple production (except for M1). For apples, feed production during the rearing and production stages of birds contributes approximately 10–42% of the total LO. For eggs, these stages account for about 10–98%. The farm area represents the largest share of LO for apples, ranging from 54 to 100%.

3.2. Cradle-to-retail

Regarding the value chain (Fig. 9), for apples, the CF of the storage and packaging phase accounts for 32–46% of emissions, with an additional 1–3% occurring during retail. For eggs, emissions from storage and packaging range from 11–50%, with retail contributing between 1 and 5%. The storage and packaging phase contributes most of the emissions for EP (2–18% and 0.7–27% for apples and eggs, respectively) and AP (7–20% and 2–29% for apples and eggs, respectively). A summary of the results from farm-gate to retail is shown in Table S7 in SD.

3.3. Sensitivity analysis

Firstly, the SA shows that if manure is classified as a waste (M3), emissions across all impact categories decrease between 1 and 52% for apples and increase between 6 and 14% for eggs (Table 5). Secondly, if the minimum land requirements (in function to the animal density) are allocated to eggs, LO decreases between 1 and 9% for apples and increases 10% for eggs. Third, if the C-seq in the woody AGB is reduced by 64% to align with some literature data (i.e., C accumulation rates around

Fig. 7. AP per kg apple (left) and per kg egg (right) in kg SO₂-eq using two modeling approaches (M1, M2) for Farm 1 (F1), Farm (F2), reference system for apples (RS-A), and reference system for eggs (RS-E).

Fig. 8. LO per kg apple (left) and per kg egg (right) in m²a using two modeling approaches (M1, M2) for Farm 1 (F1), Farm (F2), reference system for apples (RS-A), and reference system for eggs (RS-E).

1 t C/ha/yr), the CF increases for apples and eggs between 8–17% and 7–14%, respectively.

4. Discussion

4.1. Environmental impacts and comparison with similar studies

Regarding the first objective, the environmental impacts and CF of two silvopastoral case studies in Austria were assessed, including contribution analysis, post-harvest activities, and C-seq. Below, the results and estimations in this paper were compared with those reported in the organic non-agroforestry literature on apple and egg production (Table S8 in SD). The comparison was conducted from cradle-to-farm gate, as this system boundary was predominantly adopted in the literature.

Regarding the CF, the literature for apple production ranged from 0.07 to 0.15 kg CO₂-eq/kg apple (Alaphilippe et al., 2013; Goossens et al., 2017; Longo et al., 2017) in line with what was found for both the reference systems and the silvopastoral farms in the present paper, whereas Zhu et al. (2018) found a higher CF of 0.87 kg CO₂/kg apple, which could be because of the high fertilization rates and the consequential LCA approach. CF for egg production showed considerable variation in the literature, ranging from 1.30 to 3.42 kg CO₂-eq/kg egg (Dekker et al., 2011; Pelletier, 2017). The CF in kg CO₂/kg egg of 1.62, 1.35, and 1.54 in RS-E, F1, and F2, respectively (when using M2) are within the given range of these results. CF per kg egg in F1 and F2 (0.2 and 0.3 kg CO₂-eq/kg egg respectively) are notably lower for M1 due to the economic allocation. Regarding C-seq, the annual C-seq rate over one rotation period in the woody biomass was between 2.9 and 3.8 t C/ha/yr and C-seq in the soil over 100-year period was 0.03–0.2 t C/ha/yr. The estimates for soil are consistent with values reported in the literature for perennial systems, such as 0.06 t C/ha/yr (McNally and

Gentile, 2021). While C in the woody biomass exceeded some literature values, including 0.28–1.5 t C/ha/yr in New Zealand (McNally and Gentile, 2021), 1.37 t C/ha/yr in China (Yang et al., 2020), and 0.58 t C/ha/yr in Italy (Zanotelli et al., 2015), McNally and Gentile (2021) also reported comparable rates in other woody vegetation systems, such as medium-tall hedges (3.5 t C/ha/yr), low hedges (2.2 t C/ha/yr), and untopped trees (3.5–7.9 t C/ha/yr). In addition, the values for the woody biomass in this study align closely with findings from other studies on apple orchards and with similar climate conditions, such as the 3.27 t C/ha/yr observed in the United States (Lakso, 2010) and 4.3 t C/ha/yr in Italy (Scandellari et al., 2016). Several factors may help explain the discrepancies within the literature, such as tree age, tree density, exclusion of root carbon biomass (McNally and Gentile, 2021), and specific management practices, which can significantly influence the extrapolation of results. In general, C-seq remains a topic of significant discussion in the scientific literature, with limited data available for apple systems. Thus a SA on the amount of C-seq in apple trees was conducted, as explained in section 2.5.

Regarding EP, EP is less commonly reported in the literature and shows high variations (e.g., 0.03–3.5 and 14–38 g PO₄-eq/kg apple and kg egg, respectively) (Alaphilippe et al., 2013; Longo et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2018). Results for apples in this paper are within those reported in the literature (except for M1) (see e.g., Leinonen et al., 2012a; Pelletier, 2017; Turner et al., 2022). In contrast, the EP for eggs is slightly above the reported literature values (except for M1), potentially due to lower yields (in this paper, egg yields were around 45% and 11% lower for F1 and F2 respectively, compared with literature values) and the approaches for estimating leaching. These approaches include different characterization factors (e.g., 0.10 kg PO₄-eq in the CML LCIA method or 0.2 kg N-eq in the EF 3.0 LCIA method), assumptions (e.g., between 0 and 20% of excreted N could be assumed as leached) (see e.g., Pelletier, 2017; Brook et al., 2022), or modeling choices (e.g., the inclusion

Fig. 9. Post-harvest emissions per kg apple (left) and per kg egg (right) using two modeling approaches (M1, M2) for Farm 1 (F1), Farm 2 (F2), reference system for apples (RS-A), and reference system for eggs (RS-E). Production entails emissions from cradle-to-farm gate. Emissions from farm gate-to-retail are linked to storage and packaging and retail.

of climate dynamics or other unaccounted N inputs such as N in irrigation) (see e.g., [Brentrup et al., 2000](#); [Kanton St.Gallen, 2013](#); [Serra et al., 2023](#)). In this paper, negative values were estimated for leaching in RS-A and F1 partly due to their substantial C inputs applied into the soil via mulching or composting, using at least 90% of organic plant residues. This influx of C with a high C:N ratio may potentially increase N immobilization for microbial growth, thereby influencing leaching and the EP. Similar to EP, AP is less frequently reported in the literature with ranges between 0.7–1.6 and 42–65 g SO₂-eq per kg apple and egg, respectively. Values in this paper for apples and eggs are lower than in the literature ([Dekker et al., 2011](#); [Leinonen et al., 2012a](#); [Goossens et al., 2017](#); [Longo et al., 2017](#); [Pelletier, 2017](#); [Turner et al., 2022](#)). This could be partly due to the lower energy used during field operations for apples and lower NH₃ emissions for eggs.

The system boundary included three resource loops related to the silvopastoral interactions (i.e., manure, land, and feed). One resource loop linked to apple production was also analyzed, namely, biomass. Both biomass and manure served as inputs primarily for fertilizing the orchard or arable lands. The orchards also provided land (outdoor run area) and potential supplemental feed for birds, which influenced the farm-level N estimations. Regarding manure, it was assumed that the excreted manure was evenly distributed in the orchard area. However, hens may not use the full range of the farm area ([Bestman, 2017](#)), which could create N hotspots near the houses and around the orchard.

Literature values for manure excretion in Austria have been reported as 0.7 kg N/hen/yr ([Anderl et al., 2022](#)) which is close to those in this paper (0.5, 0.6, and 0.9 kg N/hen/yr for F1, F2, and RS-E, respectively). Regarding feed intake of hens, the contributions from forage were assumed to be 10%, 8%, and 6% of DM for F1, F2, and RS-E respectively. According to [Crawley and Krimpen \(2015\)](#), around 12–13% of the total DM intake of free-range laying hens can be attributed to forage. Literature values for roughage intake of hens ranged between 0.7 and 72 g DM forage/bird/day ([Bosshardt et al., 2022](#)). In this paper, an intake of 6 g forage/hen/day was assumed, however, actual intake can vary due to different factors (e.g., breed and age). The FCRs in this paper were 3.4, 2.2, and 2.8 kg feed/kg egg in F1, F2, and RS-E respectively, which is around the range reported in the literature for organic egg production (only intake of concentrates, i.e. excluding forage intake) ([Table S9 in SD](#)). The higher FCRs in F1 may stem from the lower productivity (i.e., 180 eggs per hen) relative to figures cited in the existing organic (276–278 eggs per hen) and conventional (338 eggs per hen) LCA literature ([Dekker et al., 2011, 2013](#); [Leinonen et al., 2012b](#); [Abín et al., 2018](#)). Regarding land, although the literature was limited, a study on apple production reports 0.49 m²a/kg apple ([Zhu et al., 2018](#)) and 5–7 m²a/kg egg ([Dekker et al., 2011](#); [Pelletier, 2017](#)), which is in line with what was found for both the reference systems and the analyzed farms.

From a practical perspective, management differences between F1 and F2 have been shown to influence C-seq and nutrient flows. Key

strategies for enhancing the soil C pool and optimizing C-seq include minimizing soil disturbance through grafting (as in F1) and recirculating organic inputs, such as pruning residues, through mulching or composting. Nutrient management can be optimized by improving the uniformity of manure distribution across the farm, particularly in the outdoor areas where N hotspots can form near hen houses. Furthermore, optimizing feed management and adjusting concentrate feed quantities according to expected forage intake across different seasons can help reduce GHG emissions and land use. Concerning long-term impacts, while the case studies have the potential to mitigate GHG emissions through C-seq and nutrient recycling, adding more animals to orchards than in current agricultural systems could result in higher overall emissions and greater land use demands due to the additional need for feed. Regarding biodiversity, animals in orchards may serve as biological pest controllers, but they also risk consuming beneficial auxiliary fauna (Bosshardt et al., 2022). Although manure applications can enhance the soil C pool, the carbon input from bird manure into the orchards was relatively small (0.7–9%) and insufficient to offset the substantial negative impacts associated with feed production, among others. In addition, physical disturbances from animals may degrade soil structure over time and could affect water resources through leaching, especially if the system scales with higher animal densities (Sales-Baptista et al., 2016; Bosshardt et al., 2022).

4.2. The effect of different modeling approaches on the silvopastoral systems

Regarding the second objective, two distinct modeling approaches were used for distributing the environmental impact of the entire system between apples and eggs. According to the ISO standards (ISO, 2006a), allocation should be avoided, for example, by creating sub-processes whenever possible. However, when processes cannot be separated, the allocation should be based on the underlying relationships between products, such as economic factors. M1 applied the latter approach, enabling the identification of the main product (with the highest revenue), co-products, and residual products, along with their associated environmental impacts. M1 also took into account resource loops that were interconnected and difficult to separate, such as manure, influenced by food supplementation and land area provided by the orchard, which in turn affected soil and tree growth. However, M1 may lead to assigning a greater share of emissions to high-value products like apples, potentially skewing the assessment in favor of secondary economic activities, such as egg production. This bias can result in overestimating the environmental impacts of apples and underestimating those of eggs. The alternative to economic allocation was to model the multifunctional system by partitioning it into sub-processes (ISO, 2006a). This approach was applied in M2, where emissions were directly linked to the subsystem and the specific product they were associated with. Thus, high-emission activities (e.g., feed production) were not influenced by the economic values or yields of the main product (i.e., apples). However, separating and individually modeling resource loops proved challenging, particularly when manure (associated with the egg subsystem) and plant biomass (associated with the apple subsystem) were mixed in compost, as well as accurately tracking the quantities exported or applied in the orchard.

4.3. Methodological limitations and further research needs

Some methodological limitations were encountered in this assessment and addressed in this section. The methodology for estimating soil C-seq used Danish wheat as the reference crop (for more details read Mogensen et al. 2014). Despite potential geographical differences, wheat is a widely cultivated crop across Europe, including Austria, and has been extensively studied (Heidmann et al., 2001). Furthermore, different pathways for handling woody biomass in apple orchards can influence C release (Le Féon et al., 2023). In this paper, the woody

biomass was fully integrated into the compost, thereby reducing uncertainties about the fate of the woody biomass. Other uncertainties regarding C contributions, such as pruning quantities, were minimized by employing well-established models specific to apple orchards (Ledo et al., 2018). Although conventional concentrates were used as proxies in the background database for organic pullet rearing, and French yield-based data was used to estimate LO, the database used in this paper was still the most comprehensive source for European LCAs regarding organic agriculture (Montemayor et al., 2022). Furthermore, although this paper did not model complex compost interactions, including degradation processes, the fertilization rates (i.e., 7, 52, and 47 kg N/ha in F1, F2, and RS-A, respectively) were aligned with standard values for apple cultivation in Denmark (25–40 kg N/ha/yr), France (47–114 kg N/ha/yr) (Alaphilippe et al., 2016), Poland (50 kg N/ha/yr) (Kowalczyk et al., 2022), and Norway (20–65 kg N/ha/yr) (Krogstad et al., 2023).

Regarding future research, it is worth mentioning that the analyzed case studies are not one-size-fits-all. More scenarios, including those without hens, should be explored, such as silvoarable apple production systems (Smith et al., 2014; Pitchers et al., 2017; Staton et al., 2022). In addition, further assessments are needed to evaluate whether the studied systems are 'good enough' from an environmental perspective and operate within their ecosystem's carrying capacity (Hauschild, 2015; Bjørn et al., 2020). Furthermore, other modeling approaches for handling co-products could be further tested and compared, such as system expansion (the manure replaces the organic fertilizer so there are credits from avoided fertilizer production), economic allocation (i.e., assuming manure as a co-product of the system that has value) (Dalgaard and Halberg, 2007; FAO, 2016; Marton et al., 2016; Montemayor et al., 2022), or biophysical allocation. Moreover, while a substitution approach could have been used to account for products displaced by the rendering or on-farm consumption of spent hens in F1, the broader market effects introduced by substitution fall outside the scope of this paper. Also, the consistent economic allocation approach applied across classes and other products ensured a fairer comparison across systems and models. Additionally, given the minimal economic contribution of spent hens (<0.2%), the emissions of the rendering phase were assumed negligible. Moreover, other impact assessment methods for estimating C-seq in the woody biomass and the C opportunity costs (i.e., C-seq if the land had been occupied with native ecosystems instead of pasture or arable crops) (Hayek et al., 2021; Blaustein-Rejto et al., 2023) could be examined. Furthermore, it could be interesting to compare whether integrating trees into an established egg system might be more beneficial rather than the reverse (as in this paper). This approach could involve reducing animal densities and actively replacing the reference system. Alternatively, integrating animals into orchards could be more advantageous during the initial years of orchard development, when trees have higher nutrient demands, rather than during fully productive stages (as were the cases in this paper). Furthermore, the potential benefits of the assessed case studies could be further harnessed if they are developed in harmony with the scientific literature for shifting towards producing less emission-intensive food options while complying with local dietary guidelines (Pierer et al., 2014; Resare Sahlin and Trewern, 2022). This calls for further attention in policy and research papers regarding the prioritization of food quality over quantity and yields.

5. Conclusions

First, this paper assessed the environmental impacts of two silvopastoral case studies (F1 and F2) in Austria, where egg production was integrated into organic apple orchards. The analysis included contributions of carbon sequestration and post-harvest activities. In general, the environmental impacts per kg egg and kg apple in F1 and F2 were lower in most impact categories relative to their reference systems. These impacts were mainly driven by management factors in the production phase of the value chain. Key management factors include the

methods of hen sourcing, amount of bought-in concentrates, compost mix and application rates, and between-row management practices. Post-harvest activities accounted for up to 29% of the total impacts for EP and AP, and up to 57% for CC. When accounting for carbon sequestration, emissions were reduced by 22–42% for apples and by 0.4–39% for eggs. Sequestration was predominantly associated with the carbon contributions from plant biomass from apple production (84–99%). Second, two modeling approaches (M1 and M2) at the farm gate were tested and results were compared to standard practices. Overall, F1 and F2 showed different environmental profiles under the same modeling conditions. M1 consistently resulted in higher impacts per kg apple and lower impacts per kg egg relative to M2.

The effects of integrating egg production into apple orchards were also examined through three resource loops (i.e., feed, manure, and land). Although the apple orchards can provide access to forage to animals due to the grassland vegetation, the potential additional feed availability and reductions in bought-in concentrates due to the presence of trees are uncertain, requiring further experiments. While manure had a positive effect on soil, contributing 0.7–9% of the carbon, it was also linked to leaching in M2. Although land was reduced for eggs by 10% due to the land savings from the outdoor run in the farm area, it increased for apples by 4–42% due to feed production during the rearing and production phase in M1.

The environmental assessment in this paper represents specific conditions reported by farmers from two cases and methodological choices made by the authors in this paper. Further case studies are required, and other comparative scenarios and parameters should be further assessed. More development of the LCA modeling and methodological approaches is needed for future assessment of integrated systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mónica Quevedo-Cascante: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Teodora Dorca-Preda:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Lisbeth Mogensen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Werner Zollitsch:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Muhammad Ahmed Waqas:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Stefan Hörtenhuber:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Reinhard Geßl:** Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anne Grete Kongsted:** Data curation. **Marie Trydeman Knudsen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.123377>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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